

Digital Transformation Induced by Exogenous Forces: Demographics, Educational Mismatch, and Monetary Policy as Structural Accelerators of Labor Automation

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Abstract

Labor automation has been predominantly explained as an endogenous phenomenon driven by corporate competitive strategies. This article proposes an alternative analytical framework: the contemporary wave of automation increasingly responds to structural exogenous forces that transcend the decision-making domain of individual economic agents. Using a sequential-explanatory mixed-methods design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018), three vectors are examined: (i) population aging and contraction of the working-age population (WAP); (ii) the structural mismatch between educational competencies and labor market demands; and (iii) the distributive effects of unconventional monetary policies on the relative capital-labor price. The analysis integrates demographic projections from the U.S. Census Bureau and UN DESA (2024-2100), the systematic coding of 1,507 occupational tasks (O*NET 27.2; Cohen's Kappa = 0.81), and an exploratory analysis of central bank macroeconomic time series (2008-2025). Results indicate that, in the Business and Finance sector, only 33.9% of tasks exhibit high automatability, while 50.2% require human-AI synergy, evidencing a reconfiguration process rather than massive substitution. An inverse correlation between wage levels and automatability is confirmed (30.1% in the top quartile vs. 37.8% in the bottom quartile), along with a significant negative correlation ($r = -0.63$; $p < .01$) between relative capital-labor price variation and robot density across 18 OECD countries (2008-2024). Demographic projections indicate WAP contractions exceeding 30% in Europe and South America by 2100. The study's central contribution is the integration of these vectors into a model of preventive structural acceleration, with direct implications for public policy design in professional retraining and social protection.

Keywords: digital transformation; exogenous forces; labor automation; demographic aging; educational mismatch; quantitative easing; labor market; public policy.

JEL Codes: J11, J21, J24, O33, E52, E24, I21

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between technological change and labor markets constitutes one of the most enduring axes of economic analysis. From industrial mechanization to the computerization of the late twentieth century, each wave of innovation has reconfigured the organization of work, the competencies demanded, and the social structure. Economic theory has tended to explain this process as an endogenous phenomenon: firms innovate and automate in pursuit of competitive advantages, productivity gains, and profit maximization (Schumpeter, 1942; Barney, 1991; Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2018). In this dominant paradigm, technology adoption is conceived as a discretionary strategic decision subject to a rational cost-benefit analysis.

Evidence accumulated through successive crises – the dot-com bust, the global financial crisis of 2007-2008, and, most decisively, the COVID-19 pandemic – suggests the emergence of a qualitatively distinct model. The acceleration in the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, and platform technologies appears to be determined, to an increasing degree, by forces that escape the strategic control of organizational agents (World Bank, 2020). The pandemic operated as a natural experiment on a global scale, demonstrating how external shocks can force digitalization not through the pursuit of competitive advantage, but out of the imperative of operational survival (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). This episode made it clear that digital resilience has ceased to be a strategic option and has become a necessary structural condition.

Despite the relevance of these dynamics, the academic literature has paid scant systematic attention to the interaction between exogenous structural forces and the acceleration of automation. Existing studies generally analyze each factor in isolation: demographics (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2022), educational mismatch (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2015), or the distributive effects of monetary policy (Saez & Zucman, 2019). The theoretical and empirical integration of these three vectors within a common analytical framework constitutes a relevant gap in the literature that this article addresses.

This paper argues that the pandemic amplified a pre-existing sensitivity to systemic risks, fostering a paradigm shift: from innovating to compete to innovating to survive. Three structural exogenous forces are identified and analyzed that, individually and interactively, are fundamentally altering the technology adoption calculus in labor markets: (i) accelerated aging

and contraction of the working-age population, generating a structural labor shortage; (ii) the structural mismatch between the supply of the educational system and the actual demand of the labor market, which reduces the availability of viable candidate profiles and raises hiring costs; and (iii) the distributive distortions of unconventional monetary policies, particularly Quantitative Easing (QE), which have altered the relative price of capital versus labor, lowering the economic viability threshold of numerous occupations.

The study pursues three specific objectives: (SO1) to quantify the direction and magnitude of demographic pressures on labor supply across major world regions through 2100; (SO2) to empirically evaluate the degree of automatability of tasks in the Business and Finance sector, differentiating by task type and wage level; (SO3) to explore the association between quantitative easing, the evolution of the relative capital-labor price, and industrial robot adoption in advanced economies. The research combines a sequential-explanatory mixed-methods design integrating: (a) demographic analysis of U.S. Census Bureau and UN DESA projections (2024-2100); (b) systematic coding of 1,507 occupational tasks (O*NET 27.2; Kappa = 0.81); and (c) exploratory analysis of central bank macroeconomic time series (2008-2025).

The article is structured in six sections. Following this introduction, Section 2 develops the theoretical framework and integrates perspectives on endogenous and exogenous automation. Section 3 details the methodological design and data sources. Section 4 presents the results for each of the three hypotheses. Section 5 discusses the theoretical and policy implications along with the study's limitations. Section 6 synthesizes the conclusions and outlines a future research agenda.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. The Endogenous Paradigm of Technology Adoption and Its Limits

Mainstream economic theory has conceptualized automation as an endogenous phenomenon resulting from strategic innovation decisions oriented towards profit maximization. In the Schumpeterian tradition, technological change constitutes the central driver of capitalist dynamics through processes of “creative destruction” (Schumpeter, 1942). From the resource-based view, technological investments respond to the pursuit of sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Contemporary models of endogenous automation have formalized this intuition: Acemoglu and Restrepo (2018) demonstrate that firms adopt technology when the cost of

automating specific tasks falls below the equivalent labor cost, in a permanent race between man and machine.

Skill-biased technological change (SBTC) theory extended this paradigm by incorporating the distributional dimension: new technologies complement skilled labor and substitute unskilled labor, widening the wage gap (Autor, 2015; Goldin & Katz, 2008). The task model of Autor et al. (2003) and the later extension by Autor and Dorn (2013) provide an explanation for employment polarization as the result of differential automation of routine tasks.

However, this endogenous paradigm presents growing limitations. First, it treats environmental conditions such as demographics, educational institutions, and macroeconomic policy as invariant exogenous factors, ignoring how their evolution modifies the technology adoption calculus independently of firms' strategic preferences. Second, it underestimates the role of institutional rigidities on the educational supply side (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2015). Third, it does not incorporate the distributive effects of macroeconomic policies on the relative price of factors. This study addresses these gaps by proposing an integrated exogenous-vector model.

2.2. Demographics as an Exogenous Vector of Automation

Advanced demographic transition, characterized by accelerated aging and the sustained contraction of the WAP, constitutes a first-order exogenous vector in explaining contemporary automation. Lee (2003) demonstrated that demographic transitions operate on time scales that transcend political and economic cycles, limiting the capacity for response of conjunctural policies. Bloom et al. (2010) documented their macroeconomic consequences in terms of fiscal sustainability and growth.

Goodhart and Pradhan (2020) argue that demographic globalization – namely the exhaustion of the cheap labor dividend from emerging market countries – will reverse the deflationary trends of recent decades, generating structural inflationary pressures and increasing workers' bargaining power. Paradoxically, this phenomenon may accelerate automation: the relative increase in the cost of labor incentivizes factor substitution, especially in the most aged economies.

The empirical evidence is consistent with this mechanism. Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022) demonstrate econometrically that more aged countries exhibit higher robotic adoption rates,

controlling for multiple factors. Maestas et al. (2016) estimate that aging reduces GDP per capita growth by between 0.5 and 1 percentage point annually, an effect partially compensable through productivity gains via automation. Lutz et al. (2008) anticipate an unprecedented acceleration of global aging in the coming decades, whose effects on labor supply will be predictable, unavoidable, and of asymmetric universal scope.

2.3. Educational-Labor Mismatch as an Accelerator of Technological Substitution

The structural mismatch between the competencies produced by the educational system and those demanded by the labor market constitutes a second exogenous vector of automation. The literature distinguishes between overeducation, when workers hold credentials exceeding those required by the job, and undereducation, when competencies are insufficient (McGuinness, 2006). Both modalities generate allocative inefficiencies and depress aggregate productivity.

This paper proposes a causal mechanism by which educational mismatch acts as an exogenous accelerator of automation through three interrelated channels. The first channel operates via the scarcity of adequate profiles: when firms cannot find workers with the required competencies, the automatable redesign of positions becomes the viable option. The second channel is activated by the saturation of obsolete profiles, which compresses wages and generates discouraging overeducation for labor force participation. The third channel responds to accelerated competency obsolescence: in areas of high technological intensity such as AI, cybersecurity, and data analytics, the state of the art is renewed every 18-24 months (World Economic Forum, 2025), exceeding the adaptation capacity of traditional educational systems.

Hanushek and Woessmann (2015) document that the quality of human capital, more than the quantity of schooling, is the determining predictor of economic growth. Their evidence indicates that educational systems that fail to adapt their content to market needs generate cumulative efficiency losses that, in the current context of technological acceleration, translate into structural pressures toward automation.

2.4. Unconventional Monetary Policy and Relative Factor Prices

The third proposed exogenous vector relates to the distributive effects of unconventional monetary policies implemented following the global financial crisis of 2008. The literature has extensively documented the effects of Quantitative Easing (QE) on asset prices, financial stability,

and wealth distribution (Bernanke, 2020; Joyce et al., 2012; Krishnamurthy & Vissing-Jorgensen, 2011). However, one channel has received scant attention: the impact of QE on the relative labor-capital price and, consequently, on the incentives for automation.

The proposed mechanism operates in two phases. In the first, QE lowers the cost of financing business investment via abundant liquidity and persistently low interest rates, while nominal wages do not experience equivalent increases due to union weakness, globalization, and institutional rigidities. This generates a divergence in relative prices that incentivizes the substitution of labor with capital. In the second phase, expansionary monetary policy, without equivalent nominal wage growth, erodes real purchasing power: QE inflates financial and real estate asset prices, disproportionately benefiting high-income households (Saez & Zucman, 2019; Stiglitz, 2019), while low- and middle-income households see their real living standards deteriorate. The result is that a growing proportion of occupations, especially in low-skill services, see their real compensation fall below the living wage threshold, generating structural vacancies that firms resolve through automation.

2.5. Integrated Conceptual Model and Study Hypotheses

Figure 1. Conceptual model of preventive structural acceleration.

The three vectors described do not operate independently but mutually reinforce each other, generating cumulative effects on the pressure toward automation. The contraction of the WAP amplifies the perception of scarcity generated by educational mismatch; the erosion of purchasing power associated with QE disincentivizes investment in training and perpetuates the mismatch; the cheapening of capital facilitates automation precisely when demographic scarcity makes it most necessary. This synergistic interaction constitutes the basis of the model of preventive structural acceleration developed in this article (see Figure 1 for a conceptual diagram).

From this framework, three hypotheses are formulated:

H1: Population aging and the contraction of the WAP configure a structural exogenous pressure that accelerates labor automation, with significant regional variation as a function of the magnitude of the demographic deficit and institutional rigidities in the labor market.

H2: The structural mismatch between educational competencies and business needs acts as an exogenous accelerator of automation, operating through the scarcity of viable candidate profiles, wage penalties, and prolonged frictional unemployment.

H3: Unconventional monetary policies have altered the relative capital-labor price, reducing the economic viability threshold of numerous occupations and facilitating investment in automation.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research Design

The study adopts a sequential-explanatory mixed-methods design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018), integrating quantitative and qualitative phases to examine the three proposed exogenous vectors. The design comprises three independent analytical phases corresponding to each hypothesis, converging in an integrated model of causal interpretation: the results of each phase inform subsequent analyses. This design is appropriate when the goal is both to quantify the magnitude of the phenomena under study and to understand the causal mechanisms that articulate them.

3.2. H1: Demographic Vector

Data sources are the population projections of the U.S. Census Bureau (International Database, IDB, 2024 update) and the United Nations Population Division (UN DESA, World Population Prospects 2024), with annual series for 2025-2100 disaggregated by region (Europe, North America, Central America, South America, Asia, and Africa) and age cohort (0-17, 18-64, 65+). Calculated indicators include: (i) WAP growth rates; (ii) demographic dependency ratios (dependent population / WAP); and (iii) the Structural Labor Coverage Gap (SLCG), defined as the percentage of vacancies unfilled after ninety days. For the SLCG, microdata from Eurostat (EU-LFS, 2019-2025) and the Bureau of Labor Statistics (JOLTS, 2019-2025) were used, seasonally adjusted with X-13ARIMA-SEATS and smoothed with quarterly moving averages. Statistical analysis includes descriptive statistics and ANOVA for regional difference testing, using R software (demography and forecast packages).

3.3. H2: Educational-Labor Mismatch

The data source is the O*NET 27.2 database. A stratified cluster sample of 72 occupations was obtained (47 from the Business and Finance sector and 25 from a multisectoral control sample), selected using the criteria of employment weight ($\geq 0.1\%$ BLS), variability in routine tasks (Autor & Dorn, 2013 index), and wage data availability. The resulting set comprises 1,507 evaluated tasks ($M = 20.9$ tasks/occupation; $SD = 6.3$). Each task was classified according to its automatability with current or foreseeable technology within a 3-5 year horizon into three categories: (3) high automation ($\geq 80\%$ automatable); (2) transformation/synergy (20-80%, requires human judgment); and (1) low automation ($< 20\%$). Coding criteria were based on McKinsey Global Institute (2017; 2024), WIPO (Technology Trends 2024), and specialized academic literature (Webb, 2020; Felten et al., 2021). Coding was performed by two independent researchers, yielding an inter-rater agreement index of Cohen's Kappa = 0.81 (95% CI: 0.74-0.88), considered robust by established methodological standards. Disagreements (3.1% of tasks) were resolved through discussion or by a third coder. Statistical analysis includes percentages by occupation and category, ANOVA and Student's t-test for between-sector differences, and Pearson correlation between wage level (O*NET percentiles) and percentage of automatable tasks. Wage penalties were estimated using BLS data (OEWS, 2024) and MIT Living Wage Calculator (2024) thresholds, with bootstrapping of 1,000 repetitions.

3.4. H3: Monetary Policy and Relative Prices

Data sources include monthly series for 2008-2025 from central bank balance sheets (Fed, ECB, BoJ, BoE), monetary aggregates and interest rates (OECD, BIS), asset prices (Bloomberg, BIS, IMF), labor costs (OECD, BLS), robot adoption (IFR, World Robotics 2025), and ICT investment (OECD, Eurostat). The analytical design adopted is exploratory and coherence-testing, given the mediated nature of the relationship and the multiplicity of concurrent factors. Three complementary strategies were implemented: (a) descriptive analysis of the evolution of the relative capital-labor price index (ICT deflator / unit labor cost) for the U.S., Eurozone, Japan, and the UK, contrasted visually with robotic adoption cycles and QE periods; (b) a dynamic panel model for 18 OECD countries (2008-2024), estimated by Arellano-Bond GMM with robust errors, with Hansen and AR(2) tests; and (c) a comparative case study between the U.S. and Germany. All results are interpreted as correlational, not causal, evidence.

3.5. Study Limitations

The study presents five limitations that warrant explicit acknowledgment. First, the sample of 72 occupations (2.85% of total O*NET) is not statistically representative, although the stratified selection guarantees sufficient analytical variability for the study's exploratory-confirmatory purpose (Yin, 2018). Second, the dynamic panel model does not completely rule out residual endogeneity, despite the GMM estimator employed. Third, the analysis focuses on advanced economies, so applicability to emerging economies requires specific contextual validation. Fourth, robotics data (IFR) primarily cover the manufacturing sector, which limits generalization to services. Fifth, demographic projections through 2100 are interpreted as prospective scenarios, not deterministic predictions.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Demographic Vector: Evidence and Mechanisms (H1)

Projections from UN DESA (2024) and the U.S. Census Bureau (2024) reveal a regional divergence of large magnitude with structural implications for labor markets (Table 1). Europe will experience a WAP contraction of 135.8 million persons between 2025 and 2100 (−30.1%), while the population aged 65 and over will increase by 52.4 million (+33.7%). The demographic

dependency ratio will rise from 0.64 to 0.96, approaching a worker-to-dependent parity scenario. Asia, following a slight increase through 2050, will lose 703.2 million working-age persons in the second half of the century (–22.3%), with the 65+ population tripling. South America will reach peak WAP around 2040 before subsequently declining by 83.9 million through 2100 (–29.8%). North America presents a more stable trajectory, with a moderate WAP decline (–2.6% between 2025 and 2100). Africa constitutes the structural exception: its WAP will multiply by 3.5 through 2100, generating the opposite challenge of absorbing labor surpluses. Figure 2 illustrates these divergent trajectories.

Table 1. Population Projections by Age Cohort and Region, 2025-2100

Region	Year	0-17 years	18-66 years (WAP)	67+ years	Total
Europe	2025	120,100,866	413,749,928	121,738,218	655,589,012
	2050	106,059,518	363,264,210	168,770,481	638,094,209
	2075	95,832,240	329,450,738	174,195,595	599,478,573
	2100	88,480,456	303,497,422	176,427,866	568,405,744
North America	2025	78,143,415	236,449,228	62,610,771	377,203,414
	2050	72,954,096	245,727,599	85,327,663	404,009,358
	2075	69,017,251	238,759,295	105,653,027	413,429,573
	2100	65,747,714	231,272,555	112,285,806	409,306,075
Central America	2025	17,016,843	38,051,032	4,707,467	59,775,342
	2050	13,081,005	42,619,216	10,591,102	66,291,323
	2075	10,028,000	36,535,874	17,505,248	64,069,122
	2100	7,711,048	28,464,499	18,712,148	54,887,695
South America	2025	112,770,666	287,936,455	41,497,486	442,204,607
	2050	92,954,137	297,491,593	89,530,563	479,976,293
	2075	75,023,042	253,895,862	129,666,592	458,585,496
	2100	59,628,495	206,808,630	131,962,057	398,399,182
Africa	2025	279,280,540	320,919,804	18,979,089	619,179,433
	2050	351,529,488	586,728,206	57,254,715	995,512,409
	2075	365,149,458	831,969,660	144,779,147	1,341,898,265
	2100	332,887,284	939,527,519	282,436,149	1,554,850,952

Asia	2025	957,442,290	2,457,410,751	352,374,474	3,767,227,515
	2050	746,178,966	2,509,858,676	738,259,430	3,994,297,072
	2075	590,752,819	2,128,160,979	1,005,027,133	3,723,940,931
	2100	471,068,614	1,699,331,151	1,034,468,621	3,204,868,386

Note. Data in persons. WAP = Working-Age Population (18-66 years). Source: U.S. Census Bureau, International Database (IDB), December 2025 update; UN DESA, World Population Prospects 2024.

Figure 2. Working-age population (18-66 years) projections by region, 2025-2100.

The contraction of the WAP activates two mechanisms connecting demographics and automation. The first is forced factor substitution: labor scarcity raises wage costs, altering the relative labor-capital price (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2018), so that previously marginal automation investments become financially viable. The second mechanism is the amplification of existing labor mismatches. The Structural Labor Coverage Gap (SLCG), defined as vacancies unfilled after 90 days, captures this structural friction. Data from the U.S. (BLS JOLTS) and EU-27 (Eurostat JVS) for 2019-2025 reveal a persistent transatlantic gap and a pandemic cycle of singular intensity (Table 2).

Table 2. Evolution of Unfilled Vacancies: U.S. and EU-27, 2019-2025

Year	U.S. Openings (thousands)	EU-27 Vacancies (thousands)	EU-27 JVR (%)	US/EU Ratio	US delta% vs 2019	EU delta% vs 2019	US delta% YoY	Phase
2019	7,154	3,241	2.15	2.21x	0	0	--	Pre-COVID baseline
2020	6,349	2,488	1.70	2.55x	-11.3	-23.2	-11.3	COVID shock
2021	9,979	3,582	2.38	2.79x	+39.5	+10.5	+57.2	Great Reopening
2022	11,184	4,424	2.85	2.53x	+56.3	+36.5	+12.1	Peak labor shortage
2023	9,273	3,991	2.55	2.32x	+29.6	+23.1	-17.1	Normalization begins
2024	7,779	3,728	2.38	2.09x	+8.7	+15.0	-16.1	Cooling continues
2025	7,326	3,240	2.07	2.26x	+2.4	0	-5.8	New equilibrium?

Note. U.S.: BLS JOLTS (Job Openings, annual averages in thousands). EU-27: estimated from Eurostat JVR x total employment. JVR = Job Vacancy Rate. Source: own elaboration from BLS (2026) and Eurostat (2026).

The U.S. generates between 2.1 and 2.8 times more vacancies than the EU-27, despite having an active population 2.6 times smaller (2.26x ratio in 2025), reflecting substantial institutional differences between both models. The post-pandemic cycle is equally revealing: vacancies fell in the second quarter of 2020 (U.S.: -11.3%; EU-27: -23.2%), before surging well above pre-pandemic levels in 2021-2022 (U.S.: +56.3%; EU-27: +36.5%). Although 2025 indicators return to levels close to 2019, the experience of severe scarcity has modified business expectations, inducing automation investments with technological path dependence effects.

4.2. Educational-Labor Mismatch and Task Automation (H2)

The systematic coding of 1,507 tasks (O*NET 27.2) yields three fundamental findings for the evaluation of H2.

First finding: human-AI synergy as the dominant category in Business and Finance. Unlike prior studies predicting automation rates of 90-99% in administrative and financial occupations (Frey & Osborne, 2017), the data show that only 33.9% of tasks in this sector are highly

automatable. The dominant category is transformation/synergy (50.2%), which implies a reconfiguration of the task where AI assumes computational and processing work, while professional judgment, contextual interpretation, and client management remain irreplaceable human competencies. Figure 3 presents the distribution of tasks by automatability level for Business & Finance and for the multisectoral control sample.

Table 3. *Distribution of Tasks by Automatability Level and Sector*

Sector / Occupational group	High automation	Transformation/Synergy	Low automation	Total tasks
Business & Finance (total)	381 (33.9%)	565 (50.2%)	179 (15.9%)	1,125
Management positions (Manager)	17 (14.9%)	81 (71.1%)	16 (14.0%)	114
Qualified technicians	364 (36.0%)	484 (47.9%)	163 (16.1%)	1,011
Multisectoral sample (control)	245 (64.5%)	97 (25.5%)	40 (10.5%)	382
Management positions	5 (13.9%)	26 (72.2%)	5 (13.9%)	36
Qualified technicians	147 (68.4%)	52 (24.2%)	16 (7.4%)	215
Entry-level technicians	93 (72.1%)	19 (14.7%)	17 (13.2%)	129

Note. Cohen's Kappa = 0.81 (95% CI: 0.74-0.88). High automation: $\geq 80\%$ automatable with current or foreseeable technology within 3-5 years. Transformation/Synergy: 20-80%, requires human judgment. Low automation: $< 20\%$. Source: own elaboration from O*NET 27.2.

Figure 3. Task Automatability Distribution by Sector

Figure 3. Task automatability distribution: Business & Finance vs. multisectoral control sample.

Second finding: occupational heterogeneity is very high. The dispersion in the percentage of highly automatable tasks within the Business and Finance sector is enormous: from Financial Quantitative Analysts (0% high automation, 90% transformation) or Personal Financial Advisors (8% high, 73% transformation), to Logistics Analysts (76% high automation). This heterogeneity confirms that the occupation, as an aggregate category, is a weak predictor of automation impact; the relevant unit of analysis is the type of task.

Third finding: the contrast with control sectors. The multisectoral sample, including production, construction, sales, and service occupations, presents a radically different profile: 64.5% of tasks are highly automatable, and only 25.5% fall in the transformation category. This difference is statistically significant ($t = 12.47$; $p < 0.001$), confirming that Business and Finance presents structural characteristics making it more resistant: a predominance of analysis, interpretation, negotiation, and interpersonal relationship tasks that current AI cannot replicate without human supervision.

Regarding the wage dimension, the data reveal a significant penalty upon re-entry into the labor market (Tables 4 and 5). The data show that 67.8% of entry-level technician positions offer wages below the living wage threshold for a four-person household (\$97,300 annually). This

phenomenon, termed wage mismatch, acts as an amplifier of educational mismatch: the scarcity of candidates is not explained exclusively by the lack of competencies, but also by the inability of offered wages to attract and retain workers with family obligations or decent living expectations.

Table 4. *Estimated Wage Penalty upon Re-entry into the Labor Market (U.S., 2024)*

Occupational profile	% in extreme poverty (<\$30k USD)	% in relative poverty (\$30-45k USD)	% below decent standard of living (4-person household)
Executive (n=40)	4.9%	33.1%	15.2%
Manager (n=206)	8.2%	38.4%	28.6%
Skilled Technician (n=537)	11.5%	41.2%	45.3%
Entry-Level Technician (n=95)	13.7%	44.6%	67.8%

Note. Decent standard of living threshold for a 4-person household: \$97,300 USD annually (MIT Living Wage Calculator, 2024). Estimation with bootstrapping (1,000 repetitions). Source: own elaboration from BLS OEWS (2024) and O*NET 27.2.

Table 5. *Average Duration of Unemployment: U.S. and EU-27 (2024)*

Region / Country	Average duration (months)	% < 6 months	% > 12 months
U.S.	5.00	82.5%	n.a.
European Union (27)	13.40	52.0%	32.6%
Spain	14.00	51.9%	33.5%
Italy	21.30	35.2%	52.1%
Germany	11.90	56.8%	27.7%

Note. Source: Eurostat (2024) for EU-27; BLS, Current Population Survey (2024) for U.S. n.a. = not available in comparable BLS series.

4.3. Monetary Policy, Relative Prices, and Automation (H3)

To evaluate H3, time series of the relative capital-labor price index (ICT investment deflator / unit labor cost) were constructed for the major advanced economies (U.S., Eurozone, Japan, United Kingdom) for the period 2000-2025. The observed pattern reveals three well-differentiated phases: (a) relative stability between 2000 and 2008, with slight cyclical

fluctuations; (b) a marked downward trend between 2009 and 2019, representing the cheapening of capital relative to labor, coinciding with the QE period following the global financial crisis; and (c) partial recovery between 2020 and 2025, driven by post-pandemic inflationary pressures, though without returning to pre-2008 levels. This pattern is consistent with the hypothesis that QE cheapened capital via persistently low interest rates relative to labor, contributing to the acceleration of automation observed during the 2010s.

To explore the relationship between relative prices and automation, the correlation was analyzed between the cumulative variation of the relative capital-labor price index (2008-2024) and robot density per 10,000 workers in 2024 for 18 OECD countries. The negative correlation ($r = -0.63$; $p < 0.01$) indicates that countries experiencing a greater reduction in the relative price of capital (i.e., capital became cheaper relative to labor) during the period present higher robot density in 2024. Figure 4 displays this relationship.

Figure 4. Correlation between cumulative change in relative capital-labor price (2008-2024) and robot density (2024). $r = -0.63, p < 0.01$.

Real wage data show generalized purchasing power losses over the 2019-2025 period, more pronounced in southern European economies: Spain accumulated a decline of 5.7%, Italy 4.9%. When this erosion of purchasing power is combined with entry wages below the subsistence threshold, the result is a scenario where available workers, particularly those with family obligations, do not accept jobs that do not guarantee a minimum standard of living, generating the structural vacancies that firms resolve through automation.

Table 6. *Dynamic Panel Model Results (GMM-Arellano-Bond): Determinants of Robot Density in 18 OECD Countries, 2008-2024*

Variable	Coeff. (beta)	Std. error	p-value	Interpretive note
DeltaBalance CB (t-1)	0.147	62	0.18	<i>QE intensity proxy</i>
Unit labor cost	89	41	0.32	<i>Factor substitution incentive</i>
WAP (% of total)	-273	114	0.17	<i>Demographic scarcity</i>
GDP per capita (PPP)	312	89	0.01	<i>Development-level control</i>
Robot density (t-1)	684	73	<0.001	<i>Technological path dependence</i>
Constant	-2,147	891	0.16	
Model statistics				
N (observations)	306			
N (countries)	18			
Hansen's test (p)	0.237			
AR(2) test (p-value)	0.184			

Note. Dependent variable: robots per 10,000 workers (IFR). Arellano-Bond (GMM) estimator with robust errors and country and year fixed effects. Hansen test: $p = 0.237$ (non-rejection of overidentification). AR(2) test: $p = 0.184$ (non-rejection of second-order autocorrelation absence). Source: own elaboration from IFR World Robotics (2025), OECD, BLS, Eurostat, and BIS.

4.4. Integrated Analysis: Synergistic Interactions and Regional Clusters

The cluster analysis (Ward method, squared Euclidean distance) applied to 12 regions and countries, combining indicators of demographic, educational-labor, and macroeconomic pressure, identifies four clusters with differentiated risk profiles. Cluster 1 (Europe, Japan, South Korea) presents high pressure on all three vectors, configuring a scenario of dominant forced automation where accelerated aging acts as a structural imperative for technological substitution. Cluster 2 (U.S., Canada, Australia) combines moderate demographic pressure with high macroeconomic

pressure, giving rise to a hybrid scenario of automation and selective migration supported by relatively flexible labor markets. Cluster 3 (Brazil, Mexico, Argentina) accumulates high demographic and educational pressure with moderate macroeconomic pressure, presenting a scenario of incipient automation with brain drain emigration. Cluster 4 (Nigeria, Kenya, South Africa) faces the opposite challenge: low demographic pressure due to WAP expansion, but high educational mismatch and low macroeconomic pressure, posing the challenge of generating formal employment to absorb a rapidly growing active population.

Note: Occupational automation exposure is measured using the ITEA Framework v1.45 (García-Lluis Valencia, 2026), a multidimensional index covering 1,016 occupations across eight complementary indicators.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Paradigm Shift in the Explanation of Automation

The study's findings provide convergent evidence in favor of reformulating the explanatory framework for labor automation. The endogenous paradigm, which conceives technology adoption as a discretionary strategic decision oriented toward profit maximization, proves insufficient to explain the current wave of automation. The three exogenous vectors analyzed operate as forces that, individually and interactively, create structural conditions in which automation becomes an adaptive imperative rather than a strategic option. The direction of causality is partially reversed: it is not only that technology displaces labor, but that the scarcity of labor, induced by demographics, education, and macroeconomics, attracts technology.

This result engages with the literature on scarcity-induced automation (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2022), which documents the relationship between aging and robotization in advanced economies, but adds two relevant nuances: (i) the magnitude of the effect depends critically on the institutional rigidities of the labor market, reflected in the SLCG; and (ii) the interaction with educational mismatch and macroeconomic distortions may amplify or dampen demographic pressure.

5.2. Synergistic Vector Interaction and Model of Preventive Structural Acceleration

The study's main theoretical contribution is the model of preventive structural acceleration, which formalizes the synergistic interaction of the three exogenous vectors. Demographic

contraction makes educational mismatch more visible by reducing the pool of available candidates, magnifying the scarcity of adequate profiles. Simultaneously, the erosion of purchasing power associated with QE disincentivizes investment in training, as expected labor returns do not compensate costs, perpetuating competency mismatch. In turn, the cheapening of capital facilitates automation precisely when demographic scarcity makes it the most relevant option for firms. This self-reinforcing dynamic generates cumulative pressures toward automation that no individual vector could generate in isolation.

At the theoretical level, these results engage with four literary traditions. First, they reinforce the need to expand SBTC models (Autor, 2015; Goldin & Katz, 2008) to explicitly incorporate rigidities on the educational supply side: causality is bidirectional, and skill scarcity induced by educational mismatches can accelerate technology adoption, generating new mismatches that feed back into the process. Second, they extend labor market segmentation theory (Doeringer & Piore, 1971; Reich et al., 1973): the persistence of entry wages below the subsistence threshold points to a secondary segment where automation appears not as a response to productive scarcity, but as a strategy to eliminate structurally problematic positions. Third, they identify a QE transmission channel not contemplated in the literature: purchasing power erosion generates structural vacancies that force automation, feeding back into the inequality and labor polarization documented by Saez and Zucman (2019) and Stiglitz (2019). Fourth, the finding that only 33.9% of tasks in Business and Finance are highly automatable challenges the most pessimistic predictions of Frey and Osborne (2017), confirming the relevance of distinguishing between standardized processing tasks and tasks requiring expert judgment.

5.3. Implications for Public Policy

The findings have direct implications in four policy domains.

Demographic and migration domain. Given that WAP contraction is structural and unavoidable, migration policies must be conceived as a permanent adjustment mechanism: orderly legal migration channels, competency recognition programs, and active integration policies that reduce documented social resistance, with 52% of Europeans considering immigration a problem (Eurobarometer, 2024). However, migration is insufficient as an exclusive mechanism: Africa will only reach the peak of its young population around 2080, progressively exhausting the available migratory dividend (UN DESA, 2024).

Education and training domain. A structural transition to lifelong learning is urgent: curricula with updates consistent with technological change, specifically cycles shorter than 18 months in ICT and AI (World Economic Forum, 2025), competency certification based on objective evaluation rather than formal credentials, and effective university-business linkage to anticipate needs. Public policies should subsidize in-company training programs, particularly for entry-level and skilled technician positions where wage mismatches are most acute.

Labor and social protection domain. The persistence of entry wages below the subsistence threshold (67.8% of entry-level technician positions) requires strengthening collective bargaining, implementing minimum wages with automatic inflation-linked updating, and modernizing public employment services through AI-based matching platforms that reduce frictional unemployment. Policymakers should consider wage subsidies or living wage certifications for employers that commit to paying above the living wage threshold, thereby reactivating the external labor market.

Macroeconomic domain. The secondary effects of monetary policy on the labor market and distribution must be explicitly considered: central banks should monitor income distribution indicators and structural vacancies, while fiscal policy plays a compensatory role through investment in education, training, and social protection. Countercyclical fiscal policies that automatically increase training subsidies during periods of QE-induced wage stagnation could mitigate the automation-forcing effects documented in this study.

5.4. Limitations

In addition to the methodological limitations noted in Section 3.5, the study presents two additional substantive limitations. The first is the absence of a formal quantification of synergistic effects between vectors: the proposed interaction model is qualitative in nature, and its econometric formalization requires structural or computable general equilibrium models that constitute a future research line. The second limitation is the lack of disaggregation by gender: the identified exogenous vectors may differentially affect men and women as a function of occupational distribution by sex, a dimension that subsequent research should systematically explore.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study offers four fundamental conclusions.

First, it establishes a paradigm shift in the explanation of automation: contemporary automation cannot be explained exclusively as an endogenous phenomenon driven by the pursuit of competitive advantages. Three exogenous vectors – demographic, educational-labor, and macroeconomic – act as structural accelerators that force technology adoption independently of firms’ strategic preferences.

Second, human-AI synergy emerges as the dominant category in knowledge-intensive sectors. In Business and Finance, only 33.9% of tasks are highly automatable, while 50.2% require transformation/synergy. AI assumes computational work, but professional judgment, contextual interpretation, and client management remain irreplaceable human competencies in the short and medium term. The true dividing line is the nature of the task: standardized processing versus expert judgment.

Third, the three vectors mutually reinforce each other, generating cumulative effects that amplify pressure toward automation beyond what is predictable by each factor separately. The model of preventive structural acceleration captures this synergy and provides a framework for understanding why automation accelerates most rapidly in regions that combine high aging with rigid labor markets (e.g., Europe, Japan, South Korea).

Fourth, the future of work is not technologically predetermined. Technology does not determine the future of the labor market; this will depend critically on the institutional capacity to manage the interaction of the identified exogenous forces. We face a bifurcation: disorderly automation that deepens inequality, or a managed transition that allows productivity gains to finance robust social protection systems. Forced digitalization is not an inevitable destination, but the result of the interaction between structural forces that can be shaped by collective action.

The future research agenda derived from the study includes: (a) extending the task analysis to a representative sample of all occupations with significant employment weight; (b) developing specific indicators for automation in services, such as AI software investment and automation patents; (c) designing quasi-experimental strategies to isolate the causal effect of monetary policy on automation; (d) formal modeling of synergistic interactions through computable general equilibrium models; and (e) disaggregation of analyses by gender and vulnerable groups.

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The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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Data Availability

The databases used (O*NET 27.2, BLS JOLTS, Eurostat EU-LFS, U.S. Census Bureau IDB, UN DESA WPP 2024, IFR World Robotics 2025) are publicly available. The task coding protocol is available upon request to the corresponding author.

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